

MORPHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF HUMAN SKIN AND THE SKIN OF TAIL IN MICE

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Annotation: The authors performed a histomorphological analysis of 20 mice which were fed in laboratory condition in the period from 2022-2023. During the research normal histomorphology of normal tail mouse skin was observed and compared with the normal skin of human. The results of the study showed that there are some differences in the shape and thickness of epidermis layer and the amount of sweat glands. Although huge differences were observed during the research, some similarity in overall morphology (layers, blood vessels) and sebaceous glands were recorded.

Key words: histomorphological structures, formaline, deparaffinization, skin layers, basal membrane, multicellular structures, epidermis, dermal connective tissue, squamous keratinized epithelium, epidermal ridges, hypodermal layer

Reference: It is clear that the skin is one of the largest organs in the body, with important functions in somato-sensation, insulation/thermoregulation, and immune defense. Understanding the molecular and cellular basis of skin development and function has been of longstanding interest because of the fundamental importance of skin as a biological system and its relevance to dermatology [1,3,9,23].

In the course of today's advanced development, the influence of internal and external factors on the human body, as well as on the skin, is constantly increasing. In this case, several solid factors, including: environmental pollution, the ever-increasing amount of chemical compounds in food products, the contact of various detergents to the skin, and the synthetic content of clothes and various skin treatments, including tattooing play crucial role for developing skin disorders [2,3,4,5,7,22].

Skin conditions and diseases in aged populations are frequent. The most prevalent skin diseases were fungal infections (14.3%-64%), dermatitis (1%-58.7%), xerosis (5.4%-85.5%) and benign skin tumors (1.7%-74.5%). Additionally, pressure ulcer and complicated issues after tattoo prevalence ranged from 0.3% to 46% and incidence from 0.8% to 34% [6,8,10,11,15].

Taking into account the above-mentioned cases, the number of scientific researches on the study of skin morphology is increasing. The investigation of the histomorphological structure of the skin has a great value, and it is used to evaluate the possible functional and structural changes in the skin. Also, the studying of special characteristics of the skin structure of humans and mammals is considered as an urgent issue. It is important to investigate the morphological characteristics of the skin of small mammals, which are convenient for experimenting and breeding, provides valuable scientific information for further research on human skin [13,14,16].

Objects of research: In order to increase the effectiveness of further research, to study the normal morphological characteristics of human and mouse skin. To investigate the

relationship between observed main morphological differences and physiological characteristics.

Materials and methods: The biomaterial for histological examination was fresh pieces of skin cut from two different sources: human and the tail of experimental animals. The size of the pieces did not exceed 5x3x3 mm. The study materials were placed in a fresh fixative immediately after taking. According to the rule, the volume of the fixative was 25 times the volume of the pieces.

For the above purpose, we used a simple chemical fixative 10% neutral formalin. Fixation of the material was carried out at room temperature (at 22–24°C). To prepare thin histological sections, the materials were compacted by pouring into paraffin after preliminary dehydration. For dehydration, a battery of ethyl alcohols of increasing concentration (from 40° to 95°) was used. The starting point for the preparation of alcohols of various concentrations was 95° alcohol. For the preparation of alcohol of the required strength and in the right amount, table 1.3 was used [17,19,20,21].

Table 1

Scheme for the preparation of alcohol of the required strength

Overall 100 ml	In milliliters	
	95° alcohol	Distel. water
40°	42	58
45°	47	53
50°	52	43
60°	63	37
70°	73	27
80°	83	17
90°	94	6

To obtain the absolute, we used white powder of calcined copper sulphate according to the method described by Yanin V.L. et al. (2015) [18,19]. The materials were dehydrated in cleanly washed and dried 250 ml jars. The alcohol level was higher than the material by more than 5 cm.

Pieces of materials were sequentially transferred from one alcohol solution to another, with exposure in each of them for 12 hours. Before transferring the material from one alcohol to another, the pieces were thoroughly dried with filter paper. A brief wiring diagram is shown in the following diagram (Table 2).

Table 2

Wiring diagram after fixation in formalin

Nº	Steps	Duration
1.	40% ethanol	12 h.
2.	50% ethanol	12 h.
3.	60% ethanol	12 h.
4.	70% ethanol	12 h.
5.	80% ethanol	12 h.
6.	95% ethanol	12 h.

7.	100% (1) ethanol	6 h.
8.	100% (2) ethanol	6 h.
9.	Chloroform 1	30 min.
10.	Chloroform 2	30 min.
11.	Chloroform + paraffin (under 37°C)	30 min.
12.	Paraffin 1 (under 56°C)	30 min.
13.	Paraffin 2 (under 56°C)	30 мин.

After dehydration in alcohols, we poured the material into homogenized paraffin. For better cutting, we added wax: for 100 g of paraffin, 3-5 g of wax. In order to stain histological sections, deparaffinization was carried out in special histological cuvettes. Sections were kept for 1 minute in each of the solutions.

Sections were stained using the most common staining method, hematoxylin and eosin. The main dye is hematoxylin, which stains the nuclei of cells. And eosin is an acidic dye; it stains the cytoplasm of cells and some non-cellular structures. Sections were stained with hematoxylin prepared according to the Ehrlich method. To prepare eosin, 0.1 g of dye was dissolved in 100 ml of 95° alcohol. After successful staining, the sections were dehydrated in alcohols. Sections were enclosed in Canadian balsam. For a detailed study of the connective tissue and muscle tissue of the skin, the Van Gieson staining method was used. For this purpose, we used Weigert's iron hematoxylin and picrofuchsin as the acid stain [20,21].

Results and discussions: We have in these experiments used mainly mouse skin, since it is easy to obtain fresh, and easy to work with; but its structure is rather different from that of human skin. Some features of the normal histology of the two skins are described here.

Human skin consists of several layers: The most superficial is the epidermis; beneath it is the corium which gradually passes into the third and deepest layer, the subcutaneous layer (Fig. 1). In the deepest part of the epidermis is the growth area, the stratum germinativum, along whose base lie the regenerative cells of the epidermis, the cylindrical basal cells. In sagittal section the boundary between these basal cells and the connective tissue of the corium is seen as a clearly marked and regular line. The cell boundaries of the stratum germinativum and the intercellular bridges can be readily distinguished. More superficially are found tightly-packed, polygonal and flattened epithelial cells; they form the stratum granulosum. Still more superficially the cells are even flatter and contain eleidin in their protoplasm; they form the stratum lucidum which is thin and may, where the whole epidermis is thin, be absent. Outermost is the stratum corneum, the horny layer, consisting of cornifying or cornified cells which are desiccated, non-nucleated, and usually markedly flattened. The epidermis has no blood vessels but it contains channels for the tissue fluids. Below the epidermis lies the corium, which has well-marked ridges and projections on its superficial surface; these are represented on the surface of the epidermis of the greater part of the skin as diamond shaped panels or, notably on the palmar surface of the hands and on the soles of the feet, as parallel ridges. The projections on the surface of the corium are called papillae; they are poorly developed on the skin of the face and may be absent from the skin of elderly people.

On the surface of the epidermis are found small conical depressions; these are the mouths of the hair follicles, from which the follicles themselves run down through the corium into the subcutaneous tissue. The corium consists of the outer stratum papillare and the deeper

stratum reticulare; the latter gradually merges with the deepest layer, the fat-containing subcutaneous tissue (subcutaneous layer). The two strata of the corium consist of a loosely-bound collagenous membrane, which contains blood vessels, from which loops run up into the papillae, nerves, the ducts of sweat glands opening into the mouths of the hair follicles, sebaceous glands opening into the lowest part of the mouths of the follicles, and, finally, smooth muscle tissue, the *musculi arrectores pilorum*.

Figure 1.

(Credits by Cell Biology and Histology 8th Edition) This is a photomicrograph of thick skin from a human palm. Note the sweat gland duct (DI) in the middle of the image as it courses in a corkscrew fashion through the very thick stratum corneum (SCI). The thin stratum lucidum (SLI) is situated between the SC and the stratum granulosum (SGI). The thick stratum spinosum (SSI) and the single layered stratum basale (SBI) constitute the remainder of the epidermis. The dermis is composed of two layers, the narrow papillary layer (PLI) that interdigitates with the epidermis and the very thick reticular layer (RLI) whose entire extent is not shown in this photomicrograph (X270).

In histological studies of the *skin of mouse* (Figs.2,3,), it is studied several features of Epidermis. The dermalepidermal junction was regular with an absence of dermal papillae and epidermal ridges. Resting on a basement membrane is the stratum basale, consisting of a single layer of cuboidal to columnar cells with large, round to oval nuclei and 1 or 2 prominent nucleoli. The stratum spinosum had a thickness of 1 to 2 polyhedral cells, each with a single centrally placed oval nucleus and either 1 or 2 prominent nucleoli. The stratum granulosum

appeared reduced, consisting of flattened cells with flattened oval nuclei and basophilic cytoplasmic granules. No stratum lucidum was present. The stratum corneum consisted of several layers of extremely flattened, anucleate keratinised cells.

Dermis. The underlying dermis of the mouse skin presented as dense irregular connective tissue with large amounts of irregularly arranged collagen fibres interspersed with fibroblasts of which only the stained nuclei were discernible. Numerous pigment-containing cells are homogeneously dispersed throughout the dermis. These cells had large, pale-staining nuclei that were frequently obscured by large amounts of brown pigment-containing granules

The hypodermis, and was formed by a continuous unilocular adipose connective tissue layer, the panniculus adiposus. The large adipocytes were polyhedral in shape with a thin rim of cytoplasm surrounding a large unstained space within the cell and their flattened nuclei eccentrically placed. Pigment-containing cells were interspersed between the adipocytes and had the same morphology as those in the dermis. Large blood vessels were located in the basal region of the hypodermis while smaller vessels (capillaries) were found throughout this layer. Mast cells were positioned in close proximity to blood vessels and between adipocytes. Pigment containing cells, also present in the connective tissue, surrounded the striated skeletal muscle (panniculus carnosus) beneath the hypodermis

Figure 2. Normal skin of mouse. Microscopic appearance. Epidermis is covered with a thin layer of keratin (1), epidermis (2), derma layer consisting of connective tissue (3), hair follicles (4), sebaceous glands (5), smooth muscle fibers (6). Stain hematoxylin-eosin. 20x20 ob

Figure 3. Normal skin of mouse. Microscopic appearance. Epidermis is covered with a thin layer of keratin (1), epidermis (2), derma layer consisting of connective tissue (3), hair follicles (4), sebaceous glands (5), smooth muscle fibers (6). Stain hematoxylin-eosin. 10x20 ob

Histomorphological differences between human and mouse skin.

Mouse skin differs from human skin in a number of points. The epidermis is very thin, and consists in many places of only a single layer of epithelial cells which do not at all show the regular arrangement of cylindrical basal cells, but whose nuclei are scattered haphazardly, and whose cell walls are not clearly seen; here and there the epidermis is a little thicker and a few epithelial cells are seen lying irregularly superficial to the basal cells. No regular division into strata can be distinguished; there is some desquamation of the epithelial cells on the surface but there is no real marked cornification. As in human skin the epidermis is invaginated into the corium to form the openings of the hair follicles which have the same structure as the uninvaginated epidermis; the follicles which run from the depth of these openings pass through the corium and usually pass deep into the subcutaneous layer. The sebaceous glands resemble exactly those in human skin. Sweat glands appear to be lacking, and it is not seen a definite papillary formation of the corium. In the subcutaneous tissue of the mouse there is a continuous layer consisting of striated muscle, the platysma muscle.

Although there are significant differences in the several structures of mouse tail base skin and human skin, they are very similar in terms of morphofunctional skin characteristics. Considering the results of this research, mouse tail base skin can be used as a model for various further skin studies.

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